

COMPASS

THE RESPONSIBLE DESIGN GUIDE
FOR HEALTHCARE

*Developed as part of a doctoral study by **Ihsan Kamil**

CONTENTS

GUIDE NAVIGATION.....	2
ABOUT THIS GUIDE.....	3
DESIGN GUIDE FRAMING.....	4
HOW WAS THIS GUIDE DEVELOPED.....	5
WHY RESPONSIBLE DESIGN MATTERS IN HEALTHCARE.....	6
DESIGN GUIDE OVERVIEW.....	7
PHASE 1 - UNDERSTANDING THE CONTEXT.....	9
PHASE 2 - ESTABLISHING DESIGN CRITERIA.....	10
PHASE 3 - ESTABLISHING IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY.....	11
PHASE 4 - DELIVERY, MONITORING & ITERATION.....	12
SUMMARY OF DECISION GATES.....	13
CITE THIS GUIDE & ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	14

GUIDE NAVIGATION

HOW SHOULD I USE THIS GUIDE?

1. **Download** a copy of this interactive PDF.
2. **Open** using a PDF-reader that supports interactive features (e.g. Adobe Acrobat Reader).
3. **Navigate** through the PDF; learn, decide, and design.

 Click on interactive elements to learn more and navigate through the guide (see legend below)

 Use the side panel to navigate between phases

INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS LEGEND:

- CLICK TO RETURN TO PREVIOUS VIEW
- CLICK FOR MORE INFORMATION
- CLICK TO CLOSE EXPANDED WINDOW

KEY TERMINOLOGY:

USING THE METHOD LIBRARY:

The 'Method Library' is a **supporting resource** that collates design methods extracted from core design literature and practice. 'Possible Methods' are referenced throughout this guide with a link to the Method Library.

The library is intended to **help** designers **decide which methods** they could use and to allow them to explore new methods they may not have considered before. It does not prescribe which methods must be used.

The Method Library is displayed as a **Notion database** that can be **filtered and sorted**. Pre-set views organise all the methods by Phases and Actions. Methods are also grouped by source and listed alphabetically. Custom filters and sorting can also be applied to the database.

DON'T FORGET TO OPEN USING A COMPATIBLE PDF-READER SUCH AS ADOBE ACROBAT READER FOR FULL FUNCTIONALITY OF INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS

ABOUT THIS GUIDE

WHAT IS THIS GUIDE INTENDED FOR?

The purpose of this guide is to support designers in **developing** environmentally **responsible** solutions that work within the unique realities of **healthcare** contexts. The guide can be used to improve **existing solutions** or develop **new ones**. This may include products, services, and systems.

It provides **practical actions** and stakeholder-informed guidance to help designers balance:

- environmental sustainability,
- patient safety,
- resource constraints,
- clinical priorities, and
- behaviour in real practice.

Given the unique requirements of healthcare, **trade-offs** between environmental considerations and other design priorities may be necessary. This guide supports more responsible design decision-making while recognising that **healthcare design involves balancing** multiple factors. Designing responsibly for healthcare does not inherently mean compromising patient safety or quality of care. With careful consideration, we can care for **both people and planet**.

WHO IS THIS GUIDE FOR?

This guide is for **designers** who work in or with healthcare systems, especially those who are **not embedded in clinical environments** and need to understand the context, constraints, behaviours, and motivations that **shape healthcare practice**.

It is also useful for healthcare professionals collaborating with designers, as it makes the design process transparent and aligns it with clinical realities.

TARGET USERS:

- product and/or service designers working with hospitals and/or health organisations,
- design teams developing solutions for clinical use,
- design researchers working with healthcare stakeholders, and
- educators teaching responsible health innovation.

IMPORTANT NOTE!

This guide was developed to **support the design process** and inform decision-making.

While it presents phases and actions in a suggested sequence, designers are encouraged to **adapt the order** to suit their specific needs. How the guide is applied will vary depending on project context, overall goals, available resources, and desired outcomes. Tailoring and adapting to specific contexts is highly encouraged.

DESIGN COUNCIL'S GREEN DESIGN SKILLS:

Throughout this guide, suggested '**Green Design Skills**' are listed in expanded action views. These skills were extracted from the Design Council's [Skills for Planet Blueprint](#). Suggesting specific skills provides guidance on **which skills are relevant at an action level**.

However, the suggestions are not exhaustive and designers are encouraged to familiarise themselves with the skills and use them however they see fit. The Green Design Skills were intended to be **dynamic**, this should be reflected when applying the guide.

Within Actions, **click** on the 'View Suggested Green Design Skills' icon to view the suggested Green Skills and learn more by exploring the Design Council's [Skills for Planet Blueprint](#).

DESIGN GUIDE FRAMING

FRAMING THE GUIDE:

This design guide is framed within **existing** design frameworks and principles. The **Design Council's [Systemic Design Framework](#)**, the Design Council's **[Skills for Planet Blueprint](#)** and **Biodesign Innovation** form its basis.

The **4 'Phases'** map onto the design process and outline the steps designers should follow when seeking to design responsible solutions for healthcare settings.

 [CLICK THE DIAGRAM TO LEARN MORE](#)

OVERVIEW

PHASE 1

PHASE 2

PHASE 3

PHASE 4

HOW WAS THIS GUIDE DEVELOPED?

This guide is a **stakeholder-informed design guide** that was curated as part of the completion of a **doctoral thesis**. Input from both **healthcare stakeholders** and **design industry experts** were combined to compile the guide.

THE HEALTHCARE CONTEXT:

The healthcare context used as the basis for this work was the **Maternity Care Service** offered in the **Midwest Region of Ireland**.

- The service is a stand-alone Maternity Hospital and the sole provider of obstetric, midwifery and neonatology services in the Midwest region.
- It services a population of approximately 380,000 people across the counties of Limerick, Clare and Tipperary North.
- It caters for up to 4,000 births annually.

1 BACKGROUND RESEARCH

Background research was completed to provide an **understanding** of various **topics** including:

- design methods,
- responsible design,
- existing design frameworks,
- maternity care provision in Ireland,
- design for birth & motherhood, and
- environmental impact of healthcare.

2 RAPID ETHNOGRAPHY

A rapid ethnography was completed to provide an **understanding** of hospital processes and procedures in **maternity care** provision.

It comprised of:

1. the completion of **observations** across wards in the maternity hospital, and
2. **focus groups** with interdisciplinary hospital staff.

3 DESIGN INDUSTRY INPUT

Design and industry expert input was sought throughout the development process to **ground** the guide **in expert input**.

It comprised of:

1. opinions and perspectives gathered through an **insight form**, and
2. **feedback sessions** completed with designers where critique on draft guides was obtained.

OVERVIEW

PHASE 1

PHASE 2

PHASE 3

PHASE 4

WHY RESPONSIBLE DESIGN MATTERS IN HEALTHCARE

Healthcare is a unique setting where environmental responsibility must be balanced with patient care, safety, risk management, and regulatory requirements.

Designing solutions that ignore the **realities of healthcare contexts**, such as clinical workflows, professional hierarchies, time pressures, clinician priorities, and safety protocols, are unlikely to be adopted and may create unintended risks.

Responsible design in healthcare helps ensure that solutions are:

- safe and aligned with clinical practice,
- grounded in real behaviour and everyday practice,
- sustainable in practice, not just in theory,
- compliant with regulations and organisational priorities,
- mindful of limited resources, time, and funding, and
- developed with input from relevant stakeholders.

Addressing environmental challenges in healthcare is an important **part of global sustainability efforts**. Innovations in new product development, medical devices, and healthcare waste management are key to building more sustainable healthcare systems.

Organisations such as **Health Care Without Harm** are leading this shift by working to reduce healthcare's environmental footprint and driving sustainable healthcare practices.

Healthcare Without Harm's 7 Key Focus Areas:

DESIGN GUIDE OVERVIEW

▶ BEGIN WITH A DESIGN CHALLENGE

KEY TERMINOLOGY:

OVERVIEW

PHASE 1

PHASE 2

PHASE 3

PHASE 4

DESIGN GUIDE OVERVIEW

PHASE 1 | UNDERSTANDING THE CONTEXT

ACTION 1

Explore Existing Literature & Background Research

ACTION 2

Map the Healthcare Ecosystem

ACTION 3

Assess Policy, Regulations & Protocols

ACTION 4

Understand Behaviours & Motivations

PHASE 2 | ESTABLISHING DESIGN CRITERIA

ACTION 5

Translate Insights into Design Criteria

ACTION 6

Consider Sustainability & Behavioural Factors

ACTION 7

Define the Scope of Change

ACTION 8

Clearly Define the Problem Being Addressed

PHASE 3 | ESTABLISHING IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY

ACTION 9

Explore Existing Solutions & Background Research

ACTION 10

Ideate, Prototype & Develop Solutions

ACTION 11

Test & Iterate in Real or Reflective Environments

ACTION 12

Develop the Implementation Pathway

ACTION 13

Consider Adoption & Sustained Use

PHASE 4 | DELIVERY, MONITORING & ITERATION

ACTION 14

Understand Real-World Behaviour & Impact

ACTION 15

Identify Unintended Consequences & Trade-Offs

ACTION 16

Adapt & Embed Into Culture

OVERVIEW

PHASE 1

PHASE 2

PHASE 3

PHASE 4

PHASE 1 - UNDERSTANDING THE CONTEXT

Understand real healthcare practice to enable responsible change

ORIENTATION CUE

IF YES, CONTINUE TO **PHASE 2**

IF NO, CONTINUE TO **PHASE 1 ACTIONS**

NOTE:

Use the findings from Phase 1 to **determine a baseline** that can be revisited throughout the design process. Depending on your context, this may include measuring the current state, environmental impact and/or completing a risk assessment. Reviewing health and safety reports may be applicable too.

Relevant **regulations, protocols, and policies are determined by the context**. During this Phase, highlight those that are relevant to you and ensure they are considered throughout the entire process. For example, ISO13485 and ISO14791 may be relevant when designing medical devices.

If relevant, include **considerations for training** in Actions 2 and 4.

PHASE 1 CHECKLIST

- EXISTING RESEARCH AND GUIDANCE REVIEWED
- HEALTHCARE ECOSYSTEM MAPPED
- POLICY AND REGULATORY CONSTRAINTS UNDERSTOOD
- REAL BEHAVIOURS AND MOTIVATIONS EXPLORED
- KEY ASSUMPTIONS SURFACED AND DOCUMENTED

OVERVIEW

PHASE 1

PHASE 2

PHASE 3

PHASE 4

PHASE 2 - ESTABLISHING DESIGN CRITERIA

Define criteria that are sustainable in real practice

IF YES, CONTINUE TO **PHASE 3**

IF NO, CONTINUE TO **PHASE 2 ACTIONS**

ORIENTATION CUE

NOTE:

Using the baseline, **regulations, protocols, and policies** determined in Phase 1 are critical in this Phase. Considerations for risk are also crucial here.

Strongly defined criteria and baselines present potential **measurable impacts** that may contribute to **gaining buy-in** from decision makers and stakeholders.

Depending on your context, **codesign** may present an opportunity to leverage user/ stakeholder participation further.

PHASE 2 CHECKLIST

- INSIGHTS TRANSLATED INTO CLEAR DESIGN CRITERIA
- SUSTAINABILITY AND BEHAVIOURAL TRADE-OFFS CONSIDERED
- DEFINED REALISTIC SCOPE OF CHANGE
- DESIGN PROBLEM CLEARLY ARTICULATED AND FRAMED

OVERVIEW

PHASE 1

PHASE 2

PHASE 3

PHASE 4

PHASE 3 - ESTABLISHING IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY

Design for adoption in real practice

ORIENTATION CUE

IF YES, CONTINUE TO **PHASE 4**

IF NO, CONTINUE TO **PHASE 3 ACTIONS**

NOTE:

Actions 9, 10, and 11 form an iterative loop. Designers should move back and forth between exploring existing solutions, ideating, prototyping, and testing until feasible and responsible solution directions emerge.

Depending on your context, **codesign** may present an opportunity to leverage user/stakeholder participation further.

Constraints to decision making such as safety, regulations, and protocols may arise in highly regulated environments. During the design process these may present needs for **trade-offs** and design **compromises**.

PHASE 3 CHECKLIST

- EXISTING SOLUTIONS REVIEWED & GAPS IDENTIFIED
- MULTIPLE SOLUTION DIRECTIONS EXPLORED
- SOLUTIONS TESTED & ITERATED IN REFLECTIVE CONTEXTS
- IMPLEMENTATION PATHWAYS DEFINED
- ADOPTION & RESPONSIBILITIES CLARIFIED

OVERVIEW

PHASE 1

PHASE 2

PHASE 3

PHASE 4

PHASE 4 - DELIVERY, MONITORING & ITERATION

Ensure responsible change is sustained beyond project completion.

IF YES, CONTINUE MONITORING & TAKE ACTION WHEN REQUIRED

IF NO, CONTINUE TO PHASE 4 ACTIONS

ORIENTATION CUE

NOTE:

Depending on your context, **codesign** may present an opportunity to leverage user/ stakeholder participation further.

Depending on the context, this Phase may be restricted by limited designer agency with regards to delivery and monitoring. In these cases, designers should prioritise **considerations for handover** in this phase.

- PHASE 4 CHECKLIST**
- REAL-WORLD BEHAVIOUR AND IMPACT OBSERVED
 - UNINTENDED CONSEQUENCES IDENTIFIED
 - SOLUTION REFINED IN RESPONSE TO EVIDENCE
 - PRACTICE EMBEDDED INTO TRAINING, POLICY, AND NORMS
 - OWNERSHIP BEYOND THE PROJECT CONSIDERED

OVERVIEW

PHASE 1

PHASE 2

PHASE 3

PHASE 4

SUMMARY OF DECISION GATES

 ZOOM TO NAVIGATE

OVERVIEW

PHASE 1

PHASE 2

PHASE 3

PHASE 4

THANK YOU!

VERSION INFORMATION

Version 2

Last Updated: June 2026

THANK YOU FOR ENGAGING WITH THIS GUIDE!

This guide will **continue to evolve** based on use, **feedback**, and **emerging evidence**.

If you apply it in practice and have insights to share, please contact: ikamildesign@gmail.com

CITE THIS GUIDE

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